

Third type of close packing?

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The close packing of atoms in metals are described under two categories cubic close packing and hexagonal close packing¹⁻⁴. The packing efficiency for hexagonal close packing (hcp) and cubic close packing (ccp) are 74%. From the packing efficiency it should be concluded that body centered tetragonal lattice is another example of close packing in addition to hcp and ccp lattice¹⁻⁴. Calculating the packing efficiency of body centered tetragonal arrangement, the container of lattice points is actually tetragonal.

Fig. 1. Body centred tetragonal unit cell.

Here 1,2; 1,4; 2,3; 4,3; 8,6; 5,6; 7,5 and 8,7 atoms touch to each other but 2,5; 3,7; 1,6 and 4,8 do not touch to each other. In this case $a = 2r$, r = radii of atom, diagonal of base = $(2)^{1/2}a$, body diagonal = $4r$, from simple calculation $b = (8)^{1/2}r$, volume of the tetragon = $(128)^{1/2}r^3$.

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Packing efficiency = $2 \times 4 \times 22 \times r^3 \times 100/3 \times 7 \times (128)^{1/2} r^3 \approx 74\%$.

My suggestion is that bct (body centered tetragonal) structure which has the same packing fraction of hcp and ccp should be included in the text books as the possible close packing structure.

References

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